

MICROMECHANICAL MODELLING OF DAMAGE MECHANISMS IN RANDOMLY ORIENTED DISCONTINUOUS FIBRE COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

This study deals with the modelling of the damage processes effects on the overall behaviour of a Randomly Oriented Discontinuous Fibre Composites (RODFC). A micromechanical analysis based on the modified Mori-Tanaka's model is proposed. This modelling relies upon an experimental approach developed through a methodology of experimental identification of basic damage mechanisms, using amplitude treatment of acoustic emission signals and microscopic observations. Besides the good correlation with the experimental results, numerical estimations and tensile test simulations are presented in order to confirm the damage investigation findings.

INTRODUCTION

Damage behaviour can be analysed by means of deductive approaches based on micromechanical methods. The overall material behaviour is therefore reconstituted analytically or numerically using homogenisation techniques on the Representative Elementary Volume (REV), on the basis of the constituent's behaviour at various scales.

The micromechanical reconstitution requires the knowledge of a certain number of microstructural parameters. It relies largely upon microscopic observations and damage mechanisms identification, which are identified using experimental techniques of monitoring and investigation of damage growth.

Using this type of approach, several works have been developed with the aim of illustrating the influence of microstructure on global material properties, while taking into account the chronology of the degradation process. The totality of these works proposes a micromechanical modelling, using the self-consistent scheme. They are generally based on the equivalent inclusion theory of Eshelby [1] and the works of Mori and Tanaka [2] proposing the concept of average matrix stress. Among these works, are those dealing with the application of this model to the problems of crack effects and the coalescence of voids in composite materials. These are given in the books of Mura [3] and Nemat-Nasser & Hori [4].

In this paper, a micromechanical modelling based on the modified Mori-Tanaka model is proposed and applied to a randomly oriented discontinuous fibre composite material. This modelling relies upon an experimental database constituted through a methodology of identification of the basic damage mechanisms under several loading conditions. In their works Meraghni and Benzeggagh [5-7] have contributed to the development of the applied methodology, which is based on the use of amplitude treatment of acoustic emission signals combined with microscopic observations.

The micromechanical problem has been formulated in two steps. In the first, only the mechanisms relative to the matrix degradation (Mechanisms A) are introduced by means of an experimental parameter (β), which is a function of the participation rate of these mechanisms in the failure of the REV and represents the microcrack density parameter. The second step concerns the introduction of mechanisms (B) relative to the interfacial degradation, besides those of type (A). The application of the model thus developed allows us to estimate the elasticity tensors of damaged material, in addition to the simulations of behaviour laws. An example of a tensile test simulation is presented.

MATERIAL STRUCTURE

The material studied is a composite glass / epoxy system. Fibres are assembled in coated resin bundles with constant length ($L = 25$ mm). These bundles are randomly distributed in the plane of the material. This distribution confers to the material an isotropic transverse behaviour. During material manufacture bundles are oriented in all directions of the compression plane. The stacking of packets of bundles confers to the material an aspect of pseudo - stacking.

The fibre concentration is characterised by two values, the first is a local fibre concentration $(V_f)_B$, which represents the volume fraction of fibres in bundles and the second $(V_B)_C$ the volume fraction of bundles in the composite. However, during fabrication process the total fibre content is assumed to be constant such as:

$$(V_f) = (V_f)_B \cdot (V_B)_C = 0.5 \tag{1}$$

EXPERIMENTAL BACKGROUND

One of the essential points in the development of a micromechanical modelling is the preliminary identification of damage mechanisms. Indeed, the application of an experimental methodology based on the use of amplitude analysis of E.A signals combined with quasi in-situ microscopic observations have contributed to the identification of the basic process of material degradation. This identification has led to an experimental schematic model, in which the different modes of progressive degradation are attributed to an interval of characteristic amplitudes and are classified according to their nature[5-7].

IDENTIFICATION AND CLASSIFICATION OF DAMAGE MECHANISMS

Mechanisms of degradation in RODFC can be classified according to their interval of characteristic amplitudes and can also be classified according to their nature. Indeed, according to the phase (matrix, interface or inclusion) brought into play during the advent of these mechanisms, they have been classified mainly according to two types: mechanisms relative to the degradation of the matrix, which represent initiation, coalescence and propagation of microcracks that will be designated: mechanisms of type (A). However, this first type includes matrix microcracking and pseudo-delamination. The latter is defined as the result of matrix friction and the propagation of microcracks leading to the appearance of a large matrix surface between packets.

The second type of damage mechanisms are those linked to interfacial decohesion and to any other deriving process, such as fibre-matrix friction and fibre pull out processes. These are referred to as mechanisms of type (B).

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF THE PARTICIPATION RATE (P_i^j)

The introduction of damage mechanisms in the calculation of the stiffness reduction of RODFC requires a preliminary evaluation of each mechanism contribution to the ruin of the REV.

The idea adopted here relies on the results of the schematic model [7] in which an attribution of amplitude intervals of A.E events associated to one or several damage processes was established.

We define thus an experimental parameter representing the participation of the basic mechanism (i) in the failure of the REV, such as:

$$P_i^j = \frac{A_i^j}{A_{tot}} \tag{2}$$

$$i = 1,5 \quad \text{and} \quad j = 1, 2, \dots$$

Fig.1. Schematic representation of experimental evaluation of the area associated to mechanism (1) at the phase (j).

Where (i) represents the number of the basic mechanism and (j) indicates the phase defined by a stress and strain state.

(A_1^j) is the area associated to the mechanism (i) at the phase (j), it is characterised by an interval of amplitude and a number of events (Fig 1.)

(A_{tot}) is the total area of amplitude distribution, it corresponds to the final phase of damage.

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF MICROCRACK DENSITY.

The integration of matrix microcracking and pseudo delamination in the micromechanical model relies on the idea that the appearance of these microcracks is considered as the appearance of a new phase constituting the material. The mechanical properties of this new phase are known, it concerns a microcrack and therefore a null rigidity tensor. Furthermore, the concentration of these microcracks is determined according to the participation rate of the mechanisms (A) in the total failure of the REV. Indeed, the total participation of mechanisms (A) is defined as the sum of the both mechanisms relative to matrix degradation denoted respectively by (P₁) and (P₂).

$$P_A = P_1 + P_2 \quad (3)$$

The mechanisms (A) appear at the level of the matrix by degrading it. Hence, at the scale of the REV, we can write:

$$(V_B)_C + V_\mu + V_m = 1 \quad (4)$$

(V_μ) is the volume fraction of the damaged matrix. (associated to microcracks density)

(V_m) is the actualised volume fraction of the matrix (without microcracks).

The volume fraction of the microcracks is then given as:

$$V_\mu = \frac{P_A}{1 + P_A} (1 - (V_B)_C) = \beta \quad (5)$$

In the modelling, the microcrack is considered as an ellipsoidal inclusion with null rigidity. It is characterised by a density (V_μ) and also by an aspect ratio (α_μ). However, until varying (α_μ) the application of the model for a constant density (V_μ) shows that the elasticity tensor of the equivalent material does not vary considerably and rapidly reaches an invariable value [7]

MODELLING OF THE DAMAGE MECHANISMS.

The infinite body containing misoriented short bundles and microcracks, subjected to the applied uniform macro stress (Σ) is shown in figure (2). Short bundles are modelled as ellipsoidal inclusions of the same size and having (α_B) as an aspect ratio. The representative elementary volume designated by (D), contains bundles and microcracks randomly oriented in the plate plane and denoted by (Ω) and (Ω_μ) respectively

Fig. 2. Calculation model for a composite containing randomly oriented ellipsoidal inclusions (bundles and matrix microcracks). Local and global coordinate system relative to a bundle.

The elastic stiffness tensors of the isotropic matrix and the bundle are denoted (\mathbf{C}_m) and (\mathbf{C}_B) respectively. Furthermore, the bundle is considered itself as an unidirectional composite. Its stiffness tensor is firstly determined by means of the particulate case of Mori-Tanaka's model, where fibres are totally aligned.

OVERALL PROPERTIES OF RODFC CONTAINING MICROCRACKS.

In the process of the calculation, two problems are formulated successively. The first problem concerns the introduction of the bundle as an ellipsoidal inclusion in an infinite body (D) and the second problem consists of the introduction of a crack in the REV containing the bundle previously introduced.

The average stress in the matrix differs from the macro stress applied at infinity (Σ) by the existence of another average stress due to the disturbance caused by the presence of all inclusions, denoted $\langle \sigma \rangle_{D-\Omega-\Omega_\mu}$. So, we have the average stress tensor in the matrix given by:

$$\Sigma + \langle \sigma \rangle_{D-\Omega-\Omega_\mu} = \Sigma + \langle \sigma \rangle_{\Omega_m} = \mathbf{C}_m : (\mathbf{E}_0 + \bar{\varepsilon}) \quad (6)$$

Where (\mathbf{E}_0) denotes a uniform strain field and ($\bar{\varepsilon}$) stands for the average disturbance in strain of the matrix due to the presence of all inclusions.

The stress in the bundle denoted by (σ_B) can be written, using the Eshelby's solution:

$$\sigma_B = \mathbf{C}_m : (\mathbf{E}_0 + \bar{\varepsilon} + (\mathbf{S}_B - \mathbf{I}) : \varepsilon^*) \quad (7)$$

(ε^*) denotes the eigenstrain (or transformation strain), which has nonvanishing components in (Ω), but vanishes outside this domain. (\mathbf{I}) designates the fourth order identity tensor.

According to the same scheme, the stress tensor in a microcrack inclusion is given by :

$$\sigma_\mu = \mathbf{C}_m : [\mathbf{E}_0 + \bar{\varepsilon} + (\mathbf{S}_\mu - \mathbf{I}) : \varepsilon_\mu^*] \quad (8)$$

(\mathbf{S}_B) et (\mathbf{S}_μ) are the Eshelby tensor of bundle and microcrack respectively, written in the global coordinate system.

Based on Eqns (7 & 8), the still unknown transformation strains (ε^*) and (ε_μ^*) are obtained:

$$\varepsilon^* = - [(\mathbf{C}_B - \mathbf{C}_m) : \mathbf{S}_B + \mathbf{C}_m]^{-1} (\mathbf{C}_B - \mathbf{C}_m) : (\mathbf{E}_0 + \bar{\varepsilon}) = \mathbf{L}_B : (\mathbf{E}_0 + \bar{\varepsilon}) \quad (9)$$

$$\varepsilon_\mu^* = [\mathbf{C}_m - \mathbf{C}_m : \mathbf{S}_\mu]^{-1} \mathbf{C}_m : (\mathbf{E}_0 + \bar{\varepsilon}) = \mathbf{L}_\mu : (\mathbf{E}_0 + \bar{\varepsilon}) \quad (10)$$

In order to obtain the total strain tensor of microcracked composite, we know that the volume average of $\langle \sigma \rangle$ over the entire (REV) domain (D) must vanish. Thus:

$$\frac{1}{D} \int_D \sigma \, dv = 0 \Leftrightarrow \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega_m} \sigma \, dv + \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega} \sigma \, dv + \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega_\mu} \sigma \, dv = 0 \quad (11)$$

Since ($\bar{\varepsilon}$) must be uniform for the domains (Ω) et (Ω_μ), we obtain the homogenisation relation

$$\bar{\varepsilon} + [\frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega} (\mathbf{S}_B - \mathbf{I}) : \mathbf{L}_B \, dv + \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega_\mu} (\mathbf{S}_\mu - \mathbf{I}) : \mathbf{L}_\mu \, dv] : (\mathbf{E}_0 + \bar{\varepsilon}) = 0 \quad (12)$$

The total macro strain tensor (\mathbf{E}) of the equivalent material is obtained as the sum of the uniform strains and the all eigenstrains over the entire REV designated by (D), giving :

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E}_0 + \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega} \varepsilon^* \, dv + \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega_\mu} \varepsilon_\mu^* \, dv \quad (13)$$

Using the fourth order tensors (\mathbf{N}) and (\mathbf{N}_μ) defined by :

$$\mathbf{N} = \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega} (\mathbf{S}_B - \mathbf{I}) : \mathbf{L}_B \, dv \quad (14)$$

and
$$\mathbf{N}_\mu = \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega_\mu} (\mathbf{S}_\mu - \mathbf{I}) : \mathbf{L}_\mu \, dv \quad (15)$$

We have
$$\mathbf{E} = [\mathbf{I} + [\frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{L}_B \, d\mathbf{v} + \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega_{\mu}} \mathbf{L}_{\mu} \, d\mathbf{v}] [\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{N} + \mathbf{N}_{\mu}]^{-1}] : \mathbf{E}_0 \quad (16)$$

Consequently, the stiffness tensor of the cracked material is obtained and given by:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_C = \mathbf{C}_m [\mathbf{I} + \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{L}_B \, d\mathbf{v} + \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega_{\mu}} \mathbf{L}_{\mu} \, d\mathbf{v}] [\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{N} + \mathbf{N}_{\mu}]^{-1} \quad (17)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_C = \mathbf{C}_m [\mathbf{I} + (\sum_{B=1}^n f_B \mathbf{L}_B) + (\sum_{\mu=1}^n f_{\mu} \mathbf{L}_{\mu})] [\mathbf{I} + (\sum_{B=1}^n f_B (\mathbf{S}_B - \mathbf{I}) : \mathbf{L}_B + (\sum_{\mu=1}^n f_{\mu} (\mathbf{S}_{\mu} - \mathbf{I}) : \mathbf{L}_{\mu})]^{-1} \quad (18)$$

In the case of this study, the density distributions of bundles and microcracks are uniforms.

$$f_B = \frac{(V_B)C}{n} \quad \text{and} \quad f_{\mu} = \frac{(V_{\mu})}{n} = \frac{\beta}{n} \quad (19)$$

(n) is the total representative orientation number in the plane of the material. Its has been evaluated by using image analysis and microscopic observations, such as $n = 18$.

INTERFACIAL STRESS FIELD.

The taking into account of interfacial decohesion together with the problems of fibre pull-out involves the determination of the stress and strain field at the interface, defined as the external zone around the inclusion. The stress field at the interface is expressed as a function of the stress field inside the inclusion, the transformation strain and the normal to the point considered at the interface. Considering Eqn (7), we have :

$$\sigma_B = \sigma^{in} = \mathbf{C}_m : (\mathbf{E}_0 + \tilde{\epsilon} + (\mathbf{S}_B - \mathbf{I}) : \epsilon^*) \quad (20)$$

Considering the homogenisation relation (Eqn (12)), we can write:

$$\sigma^{in} = \mathbf{C}_m : \mathbf{E}_0 + \mathbf{C}_m : [(\mathbf{S}_B - \mathbf{I}) : \epsilon^* - \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega} (\mathbf{S}_B - \mathbf{I}) : \epsilon^* \, d\mathbf{v} - \frac{1}{D} \int_{\Omega_{\mu}} (\mathbf{S}_{\mu} - \mathbf{I}) : \epsilon_{\mu}^* \, d\mathbf{v}] \quad (21)$$

$$\text{or, } \sigma^{in} = \mathbf{C}_m : \left[\mathbf{E}_0 + (\mathbf{S}_B - \mathbf{I}) : \epsilon^* - \sum_{B=1}^n f_B (\mathbf{S}_B - \mathbf{I}) : \epsilon^* - \sum_{\mu=1}^n f_{\mu} (\mathbf{S}_{\mu} - \mathbf{I}) : \epsilon_{\mu}^* \right] \quad (22)$$

The stress tensor outside the inclusion is given by Mura [3] Tendon and Weng [8] as:

$$\sigma^{out} = \sigma^{in} + \mathbf{C}_m : \epsilon^{int} \quad (23)$$

where
$$\epsilon_{ke}^{int} = (- \mathbf{C}_{pqmn}^m \epsilon_{mn}^* \mathbf{M}_{kp} \, n_q \, n_e + \epsilon_{ke}^*) \quad (24)$$

with :
$$\mathbf{M}_{kp} = \frac{1}{G_m} [\delta_{kp} - \frac{n_k \, n_p}{2(1-\nu_m)}] \quad (25)$$

(G_m, ν_m) are the shear modulus and the Poisson`s ratio of the matrix respectively. (n_i) is the normal to the surface of the inclusion (Fig. 3) and (δ_{kp}) is the Kronecker symbol. It is worth noting that the strain (ϵ_{ke}^{int}) must be transformed to a symmetrical tensor.

The normal describing the equator of the inclusion is expressed in the plane (x_2, x_3) as follows:

$$\vec{n} = \langle -\sin\theta \cos\varphi \quad \cos\theta \cos\varphi \quad \sin\varphi \rangle^T$$

The normal and tangential components of the interfacial stress are thus obtained by

$$\sigma_N = \sigma_i^{out} \cdot n_i = \sigma_{ij}^{out} \cdot n_j \cdot n_i \quad (26)$$

$$\tau = \sqrt{ \| \sigma_i^{out} \|^2 - \sigma_N^2 }$$

Fig. 3. Variation of the normal $n(\theta, \phi)$ around the equator of an inclusion.

SIMULTANEOUS INTRODUCTION OF MECHANISMS (A) AND (B).

The introduction of interfacial decohesion in the micromechanical model requires not only the calculation of the stress field at the interface, but equally the identification and the application of a local criterion which corresponds to normal and shear interfacial debonding. In this study, we have adopted a maximum stress criterion, in considering the interface as an "adhesive" having as strengths (τ^*) and (σ_H^*) . The value of (τ^*) is given by Désarmot and Favre [9] such as : $\tau^* \simeq 37$ MPa. The limit (σ_H^*) can be the matrix tensile limit stress $(\sigma_H^*) \simeq 65$ MPa. Furthermore, the introduction of damage mechanisms of type (B) in the damage model requires necessarily the evaluation of the maximum contribution (P_B) of these mechanisms.

In course of material degradation, the participation of interfacial decohesion (P_3^j) and (P_4^j) corresponding to fibre/matrix friction and fibre pull-out can be evaluated as detailed in the foregoing sections. It is hence possible to define a participation $(P_B)_{max}$ giving the total participation of these mechanisms in the ruin of the REV.

$$(P_B)_{max} = (P_3)_{max} + (P_4)_{max} \tag{27}$$

The theoretical simulation of behaviour consists in the increase of the damage variable (β) corresponding to the matrix degradation and the evaluation of interfacial stress tensor, taking into account the occurrence of matrix microcracks. Hence, for each orientation (θ) , the microcrack density (β) is incremented due to the increase of the macro stress (Σ) . However, it is evident that the onset and the coalescence of these matrix microcracks perturb locally the stress field in the inclusion and at the interface, as illustrated by Eqn (22). This therefore permits access to the normal (σ_N) and the tangential (τ) components of interfacial stress vector corresponding to different values of the normal. In the case where one of the two criteria is checked for an orientation (θ) , the interface is considered as completely debonded and the participation $(P_B)_{max}$ has been reached locally. At this stage, a reduction coefficient is introduced. It enables the transformation of the reinforcement to an equivalent one, this may reduce the transformation strain (ϵ^*) and consequently the localisation tensor (\dot{L}_B) such as :

$$\dot{L}_B(\theta) = (1 - (P_B)_{max}) L_B(\theta) \tag{28}$$

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTS.

Figures (4 & 5) illustrate the evolution of the stiffness reduction predicted by the model taking into account simultaneously mechanisms (A and B) as well as a comparison between the results obtained in considering only the mechanisms of type (A) in a first time.

Nevertheless, the experimental values are linked to amplitude distributions during the test. Hence, the microcrack density leading to the overall properties is computed and connected to the stress and strain state. We obtain thus the experimental points.

Concerning the overall properties, one observes that the fact to consider simultaneously the mechanisms of type (A) and (B) may correct the model predictions. Indeed, in relation to the variant (A), the predictions provided by the variant (A + B) are very close to the experimental values (an improvement of nearly 6 %), notably during the early stages of damage.

In taking for example the moduli (E_1) , we can notice that the model predicts a variation of around 30% (at the end of the damage process) in relation to the virgin material. This was confirmed by the experimental measurements

Concerning Poisson's ratio, the values predicted by the model agree reasonably well with the experimental coefficients. Nevertheless, due to the difficulty in determining these coefficients experimentally on a damaged material, one concludes that the model provides good estimations.

Fig.4. Comparison between the variation of experimental data and numerical results plotted versus the evolution of microcrack density parameter (β).

Figs.5. Experimental and numerical Variation of Poisson's ratio, plotted against the evolution of microcrack density parameter (β).

SIMULATION OF STRESS - STRAIN CURVES IN TENSILE TEST.

The increase of microcrack density represents the evolution of damage until the final stage of material degradation characterised by a critical value: ($\beta_{\max} = (V\mu)_{\max}$). However, a question remains: can one determine the macro stress or strain corresponding to a density (β)? In order to reply to this question, one introduces a function $\Sigma = \Sigma(S, \beta)$, which connects the evolution of the density (β) to the increase of the applied stress (Σ) (S is the damage threshold detected by A.E techniques [7]). The introduction of these interpolation functions in the modelling leads to the simulation of a tensile test. Figure (6) illustrates the linear regression representing the functions $\Sigma = \Sigma(S, \beta)$. One observes that the evolution of the damage variable (β) passes through three phases. The first corresponds to the advent and the beginning of the microcrack coalescence. This is the damage initiation where the damage grows slowly. The second phase is the propagation phase of the microcracks initiated during the first one. The third phase is the final one, it corresponds to the microcracking accumulation and the generalisation of pseudo-delamination.

Figure (7) shows the simulated stress-strain tensile curves, as well as those obtained experimentally. It is fruitless to argue the fact that the variant (A+B) offers more realistic predictions that remain close to those of the variant (A). The difference between the two variants represents 5% scatter. However, from the point of view of the dispersion of the test results, the confirmation of the agreement between theoretical simulation and experiment is justified.

Fig. 6 Identification of the interpolation function $\Sigma = \Sigma(S, \beta)$ illustrating the three phases corresponding to the evolution of damage variable (β).

Fig.7. Simulation of a tensile stress-strain curve and comparison with the experimental curves.

CONCLUSION

The stiffness degradation in randomly discontinuous fibre composites has been modelled, leading to the following concluding remarks:

- (1) The identification and the classification of the damage mechanisms according to their nature, in mechanisms of type (A) and type (B), this has facilitated considerably their modelling.
- (2) The micromechanical modelling of mechanisms (A) has led to the definition of a scalar parameter (β) representing the evolution of microcrack density. This damage variable has been evaluated experimentally using a methodology based amplitude analysis of A.E. signals.
- (3) The present model has allowed us to predict the stiffness reduction and to simulate tensile curves. A good agreement between the theoretical results and the experimental values is obtained. However, the simultaneous introduction of mechanisms (A) and (B) has improved the model's estimations comparatively to the variant (A).

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